

Building Roadmaps to Industrial
Decarbonisation and Green Economy
through EU-China Cooperation

D7.2 – Creation of the EU-CHINA BRIDGE website and social media

WP7 – Open & FAIR Science, Mutual Learning,
Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

<https://www.eu-china-bridge.eu>

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the Description of the Action (DoA)

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

The purpose of the website and the social media channels would be to communicate updates about EU-CHINA BRIDGE throughout the project's duration and disseminate its outputs to a wide range of stakeholders.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

The primary outcomes of this deliverable are the project website and the EU-CHINA BRIDGE social media accounts that are already online. This report provides the links to these channels along with a short description of their design.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

Links for the website¹ and social media channels² as well as this report.

¹ <https://eu-china-bridge.eu>

² <https://linktr.ee/euchinabridge>

History of changes

Date/Version	Status	Changes
01.10.2024	Final version; revised and re-submitted	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Changed the front page to be in line with the EU emblem rules- Added a history of changes table- Changed the screenshot of the project's profile on X
31.07.2024	Finalised and submitted	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Changed the reviewer and date of delivery- Added the Linktree
30.07.2024	Draft	Initial version

Preface

EU-CHINA BRIDGE will support the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society in both Europe and China by jointly advancing knowledge on technology innovations and roadmaps for decarbonising energy intensive industries, co-creating innovative modelling by combining cutting-edge bottom-up and integrated assessment modelling to quantify net-zero sustainable pathways, and developing the most updated and comprehensive emissions data. It will intensively engage relevant stakeholders from both regions, enhancing dialogues, and fostering mutual learning among policymakers, industries, and experts. It will deliver two open-source EU-China joint technology inventories of promising net-zero emission technology options for the iron & steel and chemical industries, two co-implemented demonstrations of promising technologies in China, and co-created scale-up paths and roadmaps of the selected industrial technologies in both regions. It will also develop the most up-to-date, high-resolution, multi-sectoral, national and regional GHG and short-lived climate pollutant emission inventories as well as dynamic monitoring of key emission sources at high spatiotemporal granularity. A state-of-the-art modelling framework will be developed, exploiting and advancing cutting-edge and established modelling tools for EU and China, using the latest emissions data, representing technology and policy options, enabling assessment of socioeconomic impacts, covering multiple economic sectors and regions, and offering high spatial and technology detail. The enhanced models will be used to co-produce net-zero pathways for the EU and China, explicitly assessing co-benefits and trade-offs of climate policies with other societal goals while exploring cooperation policies and governance to drive the global transformation and assessing the distributional and global-level implications of the two regions' decarbonisation. The pathways will be documented in new workspaces in the I²AM PARIS platform.

WI – Wuppertal Institut fuer Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH	DE	
E3M – E3-Modelling AE	GR	
IIASA – Internationales Institut fuer angewandte Systemanalyse	AT	
UoB – The University of Birmingham	UK	
ICCS – Institute of Communication and Computer Systems	GR	
HOL – HOLISTIC IKE	GR	
ITE – University of Kassel	DE	
THU-SA – Tsinghua University	CN	
THU-CE – Department of Chemical Engineering, Tsinghua University	CN	
THU-DESS – Department of Earth System Science, Tsinghua University	CN	
RUC – Renmin University of China	CN	
SDU – Shandong University	CN	
CHINACOAL – China National Coal Group Corporation	CN	
BITARIM – Advanced Research Institute of Multidisciplinary Sciences, Beijing Institute of Technology	CN	
FULONG – Inner Mongolia Fulong Heating Engineering Technology Co., LTD	CN	
BIT-ME – School of Mechanical Engineering, Beijing Institute of Technology	CN	

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1 Website

The project website is online and can be found at <https://eu-china-bridge.eu>. It will serve as an one-stop-shop for EU-CHINA BRIDGE, providing comprehensive information about the project and the consortium team, news and updates, as well as links to all project outputs including deliverables, publications, and conference slides. In addition, the website will be continuously updated throughout the project's duration and will stay online at least two years after the end of the project.

The website is based on a dedicated visual identity that has been developed at the beginning of the project. The visual identity was designed to be inclusive of all partners and audiences in both China and Europe, also considering cultural differences in terms of colours, symbols, and layout. The visual identity is encapsulated in the project logo that is shown in Figure 1. Graphically, the logo offers a straightforward symbolism of the name of the project, while the two colors selected are the red colour from the Chinese flag and the blue colour from the European Union's flag. Additionally, the font types used in the logo and in many aspects of the visual identity of the project were selected to express clarity and transparency that are important aspects of the project. The logo as well as other visual identity materials (i.e., Word & PowerPoint templates) have been already evaluated by the coordinators and the project consortium to ensure that it is attractive for all parties.

Figure 1. Project logo, serving as a basis for the visual identity of the project

The website has been developed using the open-source Drupal framework (version 10). Apart from being open source, Drupal was selected as it offers a powerful Content Management System (CMS), packing many features and extensions that can improve the website's responsiveness to a wide range of devices (mobiles, laptops, desktops), its security, and its accessibility to a wide variety of audiences. The website is currently provided in English but will be eventually also translated into Chinese. A reference to the I²AM PARIS³ platform will be also added, linking the website with the modelling documentation and result workspaces that will be developed for EU-CHINA BRIDGE. Based on the news and material updated on the website, we will also create a bilingual newsletter sent to interested stakeholders at least four times per year.

In terms of evaluating its performance, we aim for more than 2,000 unique visitors per year, 30% of whom return. These indicators will be measured through the project's Google Analytics account which is already set up and connected to the project website. The website will be intensively maintained during the project's duration, while all updates will be installed to ensure the website's security and performance. Figures 2 and 3 show the homepage of the website while Figures 4-6 show the website sections on objectives, models, as well as on news and events.

³ <https://izam-paris.eu>

Figure 2. Homepage of the project website (upper part)

Figure 3. Homepage of the project website (lower part)

Figure 4. Section of project objectives on the website

Figure 5. Section of project models on the website (placeholder titles and images)

Figure 6. Section of news and events on the website (placeholder titles and images)

2 Social media

Apart from the website, social media channels will be key for both the communication and dissemination of the project. Overall, we have created dedicated EU-CHINA BRIDGE accounts on X⁴ (formerly known as Twitter), LinkedIn⁵, BlueSky⁶, and Zenodo⁷ (Figures 7-10). Each of these accounts will serve a different purpose: X and BlueSky will be used for communication to the general public and stakeholders from the scientific and policy communities, the LinkedIn account will also appeal to the scientific community and address business and industrial stakeholders in particular, while Zenodo will serve as a repository of all project's outputs to ensure the sustainability of project work even after the website will be suspended (two years after the end of the project). Links for all channels are also provided on a concise webpage hosted by Linktree, as shown in Figure 11. The Linktree webpage is also accesible by a QR code (also shown in Figure 11) that is placed in all visual materials of the project in order to provide to their readers fast access to all social media channels at once.

While in the project's Grant Agreement we have suggested to create an account in Mastodon, from our recent experience with the communication of similar research projects, we have concluded that this channel is not as effective as we have initially believed when we were writing the proposal for EU-CHINA BRIDGE. In contrast, BlueSky and LinkedIn are considered much more effective in scientific communication in our field as many members of relevant scientific groups of Twitter (e.g., #energytwitter) have started using these platforms. In terms of WeChat, we will refrain from creating a new dedicated account for EU-CHINA BRIDGE based on the suggestion of our Chinese partners. Instead, we will forward news and materials to our partners to publish in their own personal and institutional WeChat accounts, ensuring thus a receptive and relevant audience for our communication right from the start.

Currently, our social media account only has some initial posts on our kick-off meeting and the start of the project (see Figure 12). For this reason, follower numbers are currently very low. In autumn, we aim to post at least once a week about the project or relevant topics such as on EU-China collaborations on energy and climate. Our aim until the end of the project will be to reach 1,000 uses of the #EU_China_Bridge hashtag or the project account handle and gain 500 followers on LinkedIn and X.

⁴ https://x.com/eu_china_bridge

⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-china-bridge>

⁶ <https://bsky.app/profile/eu-china-bridge.bsky.social>

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu-china-bridge/>

Figure 7. Screenshot of the project account on X

Figure 8. Screenshot of the project account on LinkedIn

Figure 9. Screenshot of the project account on BlueSky

Figure 10. Screenshot of the project account on Zenodo

Figure 11. List of all social media channels, website, and platforms of the project on Linktree

Figure 12. First posts of the project on X